

Notas breves

On some unavailable names recently posted on the Internet

Acerca de algunos nombres no disponibles recientemente divulgados en Internet

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A recently posted work (ALHEJOJ, BANDEL & AL-NAJJAR, 2016), has captured out attention because it refers to several taxa which are similar to, but not compared with, taxa previously described or redescribed by ourselves (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2015). Another issue regards the availability of the new taxa contained in this work, which does not fulfil the requirements of ICZN Art. 16 and because off this are registered as “unaccepted” in the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS, 2019).

ALHEJOJ ET AL. (2016) first refer to *Sansonia cebuana* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997 as common in the fringing reef near the Marine Science Station at Aqaba. They compared it with a number of species but not with *Mareleptopoma italica* (Raffi & Taviani, 1985) already mentioned in several papers on this group and more recently in ROLÁN (2005a), nor with *Mareleptopoma defluxa* Rolán, 2005, which are both very similar (see ROLÁN, 2005b). Admittedly the geographic and stratigraphic range of the latter is different and they are probably not synonyms.

There are two other species which we believe to be already described. One is pre-

sented as a new species *Aqabarella urdu-nensis* Alhejoj, Bandel & Al-Najjar, 2016, within a new genus (Genus *Aqabarella*) and a new family (Family *Aqabarellidae*). This species, represented in Plate 6 fig. 6 and plate 7 fig. 1-6 of ALHEJOJ ET AL. (2016), is almost exactly similar to another already known species and recently described (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2015) by ourselves in the genus *Lophocochlias* (as *L. procerus* Rubio & Rolán, 2015, Figs.1A-C); with the aggravating circumstance that the holotype of *L. procerus* also comes from Aqaba (in addition to material collected in many places elsewhere in the world). The similarity of both holotypes is stunning, including the SEM photographs of the protoconch. The protoconchs of both species is multispiral: it begins with a nucleus and a smooth half whorl, and these are followed by 2 ¼ whorls of protoconch that are clearly interrupted at the end; in total there are 2 ¾ protoconch whorls. Only with this kind of multi-spiral protoconch, could it be expected that the same species can be found in the Red Sea and in Hawaii or in Japan.

The other new species within the new family and the new genus, is

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Figure 1. A-C. *Lophocochlias procerus* Rubio & Rolán, 2015. A: holotype, 1.1 mm in diameter, Aqaba, Jordan (MNHN); B: shell, 0.87 mm in diameter, Aqaba (MHNS); C: protoconch (compare with Fig. 7.1, 7.2 and 7.6 in AHEJOJ ET AL., 2016). D-G. *Lophocochlias minutissimus* (Pilsbry, 1921). D-F: shells, 0.9, 0.85, 0.82 mm in diameter, Aqaba, Jordan (MHNS); G: protoconch (compare with Fig. 6.3 to 6.5 in Alhejoj et al. 2016).

Figura 1. A-C. *Lophocochlias procerus* Rubio & Rolán, 2015. A: holotipo, 1,1 mm de diámetro, Aqaba, Jordania (MNHN); B: concha, 0,87 mm de diámetro, Aqaba (MHNS); C: protoconcha (compárese con las Fig. 7.1, 7.2 y 7.6 en AHEJOJ ET AL., 2016). D-G. *Lophocochlias minutissimus* (Pilsbry, 1921). D-F: conchas, 0,9, 0,85, 0,82 mm de diámetro, Aqaba, Jordania (MHNS); G: protoconcha (compárese con las Fig. 6.3 a 6.5 en Alhejoj et al. 2016).

named *Aqabarella pulchella* Alhejoj, Bandel & Al-Najjar, 2016. In our opinion, this species matches in all respects one that was already figured (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2015: figs. 3A-C) and what was considered to be *Lophocochlias minutissimus* (Pilsbry, 1921). We show here representative shells (Figs. 1D-G).

To summarize, the description of these two species of *Aqabarella* is based on specimens of two species previously known in the genus *Lophocochlias*, which

is currently placed in the family Tornidae (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2015). Anyway those names do not comply with ICZN requirements (species-group names should have explicitly designated type material in order to be available, the genus group names should be based on an available type species and the family name, on an available genus) so are not available, in addition to being junior synonyms if they were validly published names.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ALHEJOJ I., BANDEL K. & AL-NAJJAR T. 2016. Pickworthiidae and Aqabarellidae new family (Caenogastropoda, Mollusca) of Aqaba, Jordan: their larval shells and remarks about their evolution and relation. *Natural Science*, 8: 403-430, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/ns.2016.89044>
- ROLÁN E. 2005a. *Malacological Fauna from the Cape Verde Archipelago*. Conchbooks, Hackenheim, 482 pp, 85 pls.
- ROLÁN E. 2005b. A new species of *Mareleptopoma* (Mollusca, Pickworthiidae) from the Cape Verde Archipelago. *Gloria Maris*, 44 (1-2): 1-9.
- RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2015. The genus *Lophocochlias* Pilsbry, 1921 (Gastropoda, Tornidae) in the Indo-West Pacific. *Novapex*, 16 (4): 105-120.
- WORMS EDITORIAL BOARD, 2019. World Register of Marine Species. Available from <http://www.marinespecies.org/> at the Flaners Marine Institute, retrieved 20-05-2019.

Notes of "Iberus" editor

(1) Before this note was accepted, on May 25, 2019, the editor attempted to contact Ikhlas Alhejoj, Klaus Bandel and Tariq Al-Najjar. The third e-mail turned out to be invalid and the other two remained without a reply.

(2) The journal "Natural Science" claims an ISSN 2150.4091 for a printed version. However it was not possible to trace any printed copy of the journal in mainstream library catalogs: <https://www.worldcat.org/>, <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/>, <http://www.sudoc.abes.fr/>, <https://trove.nla.gov.au/>. The publisher's website does not contain either any instructions regarding distribution of printed copies, so that it is concluded that the journal is distributed online only. Therefore, it is subject to the requirements of ICZN Art. 8.5 (amended) that a ZooBank registration be stated in the article, and that the journal be housed in a permanent repository in addition to the publisher's website. This makes an additional reason (else than the criteria of ICZN Art. 16) for having these names unavailable.

